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MYTHOPOETICS OF MELVILLE'S NOVEL "MOBY DICK"

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Abstract

The main work of Herman Melville, the final work of the literature of American Romanticism. A long novel with numerous lyrical digressions, imbued with biblical imagery and multilayered symbolism, was not understood and accepted by contemporaries. The novel was written quickly. 760 pages took less than two years. So, in 1851, Moby Dick was published - a novel, or rather a poem, the American version of the Bronze Horseman, about the exorbitant pride of Captain Ahab, who planned to take revenge on the elements, and about the helpless wisdom of his assistant Starbuck, who decided to raise his hand against his distraught captain. The article analyzes H. Melville's novel "Moby Dick" in a mythological context. Changes in artistic ontology based on mythopoetics, contamination of the epic and the novel, and forms of identification of consciousness and space, human existence are taken into account. The change in the novel of reconciliation, and mythological thinking. The novel also analyzes the mytho-symbolism of things, sacrifice, initiation, carnival laughter and other issues. At the heart of this unique work is the pursuit of a white whale. An exciting plot, epic sea paintings, a description of vivid human characters in harmonious combination with philosophical generalizations make the book a masterpiece of world literature.

Keywords: mythopoetics, "Moby Dick", world model

Introduction. Although Melville's appeal to myth, mythological representations, ancient religious systems and beliefs was especially widely studied in Western and American literary studies, this problem remained unnoticed in Azerbaijani literary and artistic thought.

The mythopoetics of Melville's novel "Moby Dick" is distinctive. Mythological archetypes, mythologemes of the novel make up its "visible paradigm". "The text of any myth consists of revealing (exploit) and hiding (implicit) layers. Just as the structure of a myth has a closed-repeating structure, its creation (birth) and transformation (death and replacement with a new myth) are based on the same structure." [5, p.19]

Structural and thematic basis "Moby Dick" is an archaic sacrificial mythical. The final meaning and purpose of the act of bloody hunting in Moby Dick is the production of oil, that is, the creation of the substance of light and life. It also turns the whale sacrifice into an optimistic life-affirming act.

The writer was very close to the ideas of death and resurrection. Whaling is described as a difficult, painstaking multi-stage process, as an act of demiurge: death itself has such creative power. After all, the whale carcass is a source of fat and light.

The mythological structure of sacrifice can also be applied to the artistic depiction of historical experience, for example, the early Puritan concept of America or the New World.

The main part. In Franklin's monograph "The Awakening of the Gods: Melville's mythology", the cosmic struggle of Ahab and Moby Dick is identified with the correspondence of ancient Egyptian mythological layers. B. Franklin believes that Melville directly linked the source of the Jewish religion with Egyptian

mythology. The image of Ahab "falling dead" after three days and three nights of fighting with a white whale includes both Osiris and Jesus Christ. At the heart of the work "Moby Dick" "according to Franklin lies the ancient Egyptian god Set, who personified evil – the ancient Greeks called him "Typhon" – and his struggle with the God of the seasons Osiris. "The struggle of Osiris and Typhon - the initial basis of the struggle of Ahab and Moby Dick" [4, p. 183]

C. Fraser, M. Eliade, Y. Burkhardt, R. Girard, V. In the theories of Toporov and other researchers, the problem of sacrifice is considered in different aspects and it is concluded that the idea of sacrifice is an integral part of the entire initiation rite. The act of murder is committed for the sake of resurrection.

The archetype of sacrifice, according to the researchers, comes primarily from Melville's worldview. The conflicts of life and death, death and resurrection are an inseparable whole for him. In the mythological picture of the world, characteristic of the writer's artistic thinking, death and life are interrelated realities. In Moby Dick, the sacrifice model projects a plot-shaped layout of the work. Melville's novel is devoted to the stages of hunting, killing, chopping, burning animals, that is, sacrifice. The whaling fleet of the XIX century, armed with all possible technical means, is in fact no different from the ancient hunting tribes.

The semantics of sacrifice is manifested at the transitional stages of a person's life, occurs in initiation rituals built according to the "life-death-life" scheme. In Moby Dick, the theme of initiation is connected with the image of Ishmael, as well as with the image of Ahab on a more intense and dramatic level. In fact, his whole life consists of initiation trials. 40 years of Ahab's continuous sailing on the seas remind of the forty-year

journey of the Jews in the desert, which corresponds to the forty days of the solitude of Jesus Christ and the refusal of food. Ahab's forty-year sea voyages are periods of preparation, deprivation, "closure", "slavery".

Melville's Novel "Moby Dick" is associated with factography, and scientists associate its richness with concreteness with the everyday description of the novel. But according to other approaches, in Melville's novel "a double point of view" [A.Zverev's poetics is based on the synthesis of metaphor with "empiricism". The subject-material emblemality inherent in the writer's style is associated with a puritanical mentality: any object or event is a divine sign, in material symbols it has a divine (transcendent) essence. In Melville, sometimes things are also depicted alive -this is connected not only with literary anthropomorphism or the transcendent revival of the world, but also with the idea of believing in the mysterious, mystical power of objects. "After all, there is something mysterious, meaning hidden in all things, otherwise all these things will have no value." [3, p. 459]

In Moby Dick, the image of the ship symbolizes the model of Melville's artistic world. The spatial structure of the ship is based on general mythological principles, cosmologized.

In the space of the ship, the opposition "cosmos-chaos" corresponds to the upper part of the ship and the lower, underwater part. The ship-world is a huge spherical body, the vertical of which "Door-hold" symbolizes the vertical double (double) structure of the world: upper (sky) and lower (oceanic crust).

In the mythology of many peoples, death is associated with the element of water. The mythology of water includes not only cosmogonic myths, but also eschatological myths.

The ship "Pequod" (the mythological image of the ship of death), floating in the World Ocean, gradually enters the lower sphere of the globe. In Melville's works, being in the "lower" worlds is one of the important elements of the rites of passage – the process of transition from one world to another. The Douro ship represents the world axis, forming the mythological world of the whaler. The captain stood on the deck as if crucified on a cross.

The ocean, the subzone of the globe are connected with its zoomorphic creatures. Melville's Moby Ducky embodies the dragon (or snake) archetype. The archaic plot of the "battle with the dragon" appears in the novel as an archetypal motif and acquires a national aspect. "In Chinese and Iranian mythology, a dragon living in the dark world is an enemy of the Sun god. There is a struggle between them. This battle ends with the defeat of the Sun by the dragon, who receives power from Ah-ri-man." [1, p.26]. From this point of view, the struggle of American Messianism with the forces of evil can also be seen as a mythological expression of the Puritan idea. According to Cook, the "white whale" is a totem, and the crew of the ship that went out to hunt it is a primitive tribe. Physically defeated, Ahab symbolizes the inadequacy of magic as a means of controlling the forces of nature" [4, p.179]. Referring to the semantic and symbolic similarity of the words "Typhon" and "Typhoon", B. Franklin writes that the typhoon, which

the ship Ahab is fighting, is one of the forms of typhus manifestation." [4, p. 184]

The intersection of the Dor tree looks like a cross, it is a place of torture and suffering. The connection of Ahab with the Dor tree resembles the motif of sacrifice. Like Jesus Christ crucified on a cross post, like Odin hanged on a tree, Melville's hero suffers on a Doric tree. The mystical connection of Ahab and the Pequod with the Dor tree is so deep that one has to believe in the unity of man-tree, tree-living being.

In Moby Dick, the images of food and laughter have mythological roots. The connection between food and laughter is more vividly reflected in the image of Captain Stubb. Stubb is both a ship's "clown" and an excellent gourmet. Stubb is a clown, a comic actor, a carrier of carnival starts. Stubb is a "fearlessly cheerful character". (In the sense of M. Bakhtin) for him, death and misfortune are common things. If the natural world itself is not free from death, then it is necessary to include it in the process of resurrection and feeding.

In addition to philosophical laughter in "Moby Dick" there is also carnival, mythological laughter associated with the material and bodily sphere of life. Carnival element, at first glance alien to the monumental epic triumph of Melville, eccentricity comes from the work of Rabelais. In Moby Dick, the "Rabble context" is primarily related to the topic of food. The motives and techniques of Rabelais can be seen in the "gastro-nomic" scenes of the novel.

The cook's sermon, parodying the church service in "Moby Dick" ("Stubb's dinner"), is one of the most striking carnival forms. N.Mehdi Referring to the idea of the Russian literary critic and writer Yu.Tynyanova, writes that "parody in art, that is, ridiculing any artistic work, artist, even genre, is aimed at depriving them of their meaning.[Mehdi, p.40] here the laughter is directed against the "sacred", high values that permeate the postulates of Christian spirituality. The denunciation of holiness is a tradition of the folklore culture of laughter.

"Hey, cook," Stub suddenly tapped the old man on the shoulder, "cook, go away, listen, are you, the damned devil, preaching or scolding them? Cook, they don't even talk to sinners!

... The old man continued:

- You're a shark, there's gluttony in your veins, but I'll tell you, as a brother, gluttony is bad... well, a bad thing ... Damn it, you're feeding on the devil! Don't you feel disgusted? Did you hear a word? You won't hear if you slap your tail and show your teeth!

- In order! I accuse you of being gluttonous! It's in your blood! Nothing can be done! But let's change your nature! Look, you are a shark, defeat the shark inside you, you will become an angel! Because, in life, every angel has been defeated by sharks... You can try at least do it once! Don't pull a fat piece out of the mouth of our loved one, do you hear? In relation to the whale, you will have equal rights! Damn it! None of you had a right to this whale! This whale has grown up... but let's make sure that the big mouth has a small stomach, a stomach... do not take him large pieces, but take such a piece so that you can feed a small shark, because its mouth did not reach him." [3, p.329]

The cosmogonic semantics of the act of eating was studied by Freudenberg [6, p.64]. The act of a collective meal on the Ark determines the act of Resurrection.

Conclusion. The mythopoetic beginning "Moby Dick" manifests itself at every level of the plot, including at the subject-everyday level. "Things" are a kind of microcosm existing in the space of rich symbolic meanings "Moby Dick." For example, one of the notable things in the novel is the doubloon. The dowel driven into the Pequod's dorm mast is interpreted differently. "... he stood in both turns and carefully looked at the object in front of him; when he slowed down at the compass cabinet, this object was a sharpened compass arrow, and he focused his whole gaze on this object; these hard glances were sharp as a spear, sharp; when he turned again and reached the sail of the middle Dor, he stopped again; the same sharp, sharp glances froze on the doubloon, that is, on a gold coin attached to a wooden post, his gaze retained its constant determination, and perhaps there were anger and longing were involved; there were even signs of hope in that look.

But one day, towards morning, Ahab stood in front of this gold coin, rolling his eyes at the inscriptions and images on the coin; this time he wanted to connect the hidden, mysterious meanings on this coin with his stupid and annoying thoughts." [3, p. 459]

For all the heroes, this coin is actually a mirror reflecting their individual essence. All interpretations about the coin are individual and subjective, express the worldview of everyone. That is, the more people there are, the more semantic interpretations of things exist. According to Melville, all conclusions and interpretations are relative, not reaching the truth in full. The mystery of the double is equated with the mystery of the "main character" of the novel - Moby Dick.

Starting from the first chapter of the novel "Lumings" - "Mirage" - the metaphor of the loom is repeated on most of its pages. One of the meanings of the word "loom" is a loom. The loom metaphor points to the many symbolic associations and allusions underlying the work. It is no coincidence that in the material world of the novel, a whole group of objects is associated with traditional mythological images of "weaving, weaving".

For example, in the chapter "The Mat Maker", the work of knitting threads begins to take on a metaphorical meaning. "Kwikek was a master of weaving nets, and I was his student or assistant. I used my own finger instead of a loom when I let them go through the long threads; and Queek, who stood on his own, often inserted his long oak Dagger between the threads, and his eyes dived into the distance without looking at his hand or thinking about it, tightening the transverse fibers; there was a strange bed on the ship and at sea silence; this serenity was sometimes disturbed by hoarse blows on wood, and it seemed to me that the loom of time was standing in front of me, and I was just a pendulum, involuntarily weaving it back and forth, weaving my fate." [3, p.250]

Ropes, chains, ropes on the "Pequod" are, in fact, ropes of fate that bind together the entire crew of the ship, whalers, make them dependent on each other. The image of a rope (rope) had an ancient mythological function, and also symbolized universal "attachment".

The novel by H. Melville "Moby Dick" has a complex genre-plot organization, contains mythological plots and images. Mythological situations ("fighting the dragon", initiation, sacrifice, etc.) form the cosmogony of Rum

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